

Additional file 4: BUSCO analysis against the embryophyta lineage database comparing the last *Pinus de novo* transcriptomes published. *P. patula* v1.0 (Visser et al. 2015); *P. patula* v2.0 and *P. tecunumanii* (Visser et al. 2018).

